

Maintainers and restorers identified in some rice cultivars of Pakistan

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We crossed 38 aromatic and nonaromatic local rice varieties and lines with IR58025 A and IR62829 A wild abortive (WA) cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines from IRRI during 1994 kharif season. Seventy-six F₁ hybrids, their male parents, and two isogenic maintainers were transplanted in rows of 30 plants with 23-cm spacing on each side. The crop received 120 kg N ha⁻¹ and 60 kg P ha⁻¹. Standard agronomic and plant protection measures were used.

Ten plants from each hybrid were labeled. Three panicles from each of these plants were marked and bagged before flowering. Spikelet fertility was calculated as a percentage of filled grains. Five spikelets from the upper part of each panicle were collected before anthesis and fixed in 70% alcohol. Two to three anthers from each spikelet were placed onto a glass slide, squashed in 1% IKI solution, and screened for sterile and fertile pollens. Fertile pollens, which became deeply stained, were round and fully developed.

Male parents of the hybrids with 100% pollen and spikelet sterility were classified as potential maintainers, those with 80-100% pollen and spikelet fertility as restorers, and the rest as partial restorers.

Frequency of maintainers (63%) was much higher than that of restorers among 76 hybrids tested (see table). 1021-8 and KS282 were the only potential restorers for both CMS lines, whereas Basmati 385 restored fertility only in IR58025 A (>80%), indicating that marked cytoplasmic nuclear interaction exists and expression of restorer genes varies with the genetic background of

Maintainer and restorer lines identified for IRRI CMS lines at Kala Shah Kaku, Pakistan. 1994 95.

Pollen parent	Spikelet fertility of hybrids with ^a	
	IR58025 A	IR62829 A
KS282	R	R
IR6	B	B
49744	PR	PR
4048-3	B	B
Basmati 385	R	PR
4029-A	PR	PR
4029-B	B	B
4439	PR	PR
50189-8-6	PR	PR
40555	PR	PR
GP-6	B	B
GP-10	PR	PR
GP-15	B	B
GP-16	B	B
GP-43	B	B
4029-2	B	B
4029-3	PR	PR
Basmati 5854	PR	PR
47456	B	B
PK3732-28	B	B
C622	PR	PR
Jhona 349	PR	PR
PK3717-12	B	B
PK3727-2	B	B
DR82	B	B
Basmati 370	B	B
1021-8	R	R
4289	B	B
4334	B	B
4365	B	B
PK3355-5-1-4	B	B
PK3303-7-2	B	B
49818	B	B
33608	B	B
50020	B	B
50021	B	B
Basmati 198	B	B
Basmati 6129	PR	PR

^aR = restorer (80-100% pollen and spikelet fertility).
PR = partial restorer (5-79% pollen and spikelet fertility).
B = maintainer (100% pollen and spikelet sterility).

female parents. Apparently, restorers among Pakistani rice cultivars are scarce.

Maintainer lines identified are being used in a backcrossing program for inducing CMS in local germplasm. Restorer lines 1021-8, KS282, and Basmati 385 will be used to develop new hybrid combinations. ■

Development of rice cytoplasmic male sterile line 47456 A in Kala Shah Kaku, Pakistan

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Hybrid rice research was initiated at Kala Shah Kaku in 1991. We crossed IRRI cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines IR58025 A and IR62829 A, with wild abortive (WA) cytoplasm, with aromatic rice breeding line 47456 in 1992. 47456 [4048-3/PK4112 (Basmati 370/4439)] has extra-long grains and short stature, and flowers early. Plants in the F₁ were raised in 1993. Crosses of IR58025 A and IR62829 A with 47456 showed complete pollen sterility as well as spikelet sterility under bagged conditions (see table).

Backcrosses were made with recurrent parent 47456. The derived progenies (F₁, BC₁, and BC₂) and the parents were transplanted in the field in rows of 30 plants at 23-cm spacing from each side in Jul 1995. The crop received 120 kg N ha⁻¹ and 60 kg P ha⁻¹. Standard agronomic and plant protection measures were followed.

Ten plants from each generation were selected, with three panicles from each plant bagged before flowering. Spikelet fertility was calculated as the percentage of filled grains. Five spikelets from the upper part of each panicle were collected before anthesis and fixed in 70% alcohol. Two to three anthers from each spikelet were squashed in 1% IKI solution to determine pollen sterility. Complete pollen sterility was observed in the F₁ and backcross generations, indicating successful transfer of CMS from IR58025 A and IR62829 A into Basmati line 47456. Restorers for the Basmati CMS line 47456 A are being identified. ■

Pollen and spikelet sterility of parents, F₁, BC₁, and BC₂ generations at Kala Shah Kaku, Pakistan. 1995.

	Plant height (cm)	Days to 50% flowering	Pollen sterility (%)	Spikelet sterility on bagging (%)
<i>Parent</i>				
IR58025 A	97.1	84	100	100
IR62829 A	85.5	83	100	100
47456	90.1	85	10	13.5
<i>F₁</i>				
IR58025 A/47456	99.1	92	100	100
IR62829 A/47456	92.2	90	100	100
<i>BC₁</i>				
IR58025 A/(47456) ^a	99.3	95	100	100
IR62829 A/(47456)	94.4	90	100	100
<i>BC₂</i>				
IR58025 A/(47456) ^b	99.5	90	100	100
IR62829 A/(47456)	94.6	89	100	100

^a= generation 1. ^b = generation 2.

Comparison of promoters and selectable marker genes for indica rice transformation

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Several selectable marker genes (*nptII*, *hptII*, *dhfr*; *bar*; and *csr1*) have been used for cereal transformation. However, the *bar* gene and, to a lesser degree, the *hpt* gene, have been the most commonly used in recent years. A comparison of the efficacy of these selectable marker genes in indica rice has not been previously reported.

Transient expression of GUS in electroporated protoplasts and bombarded suspension cells. Plasmids with the *gus* gene under the control of promoters pCaMV35S-*gus*, pEmu-*gus*, pRoC-*gus*, and pAct1-*gus* were electroporated into protoplasts. Similarly, pCaMV35S-*gus*, pEmu-*gus*, pAct1-*gus*, and pUbi1-*gus* were used to bombard suspension cells. Except for the RoC promoter, which directs vascular-specific expression, GUS expression was detectable under the control of all promoters tested. Constitutive promoters Act1 and Ubi1 gave the highest expression levels. The order of promoter

strength (from strong to weak) in nonorganized cells of indica rice Chinsurah Boro II was Ubi1 > Act1 > Emu > CaMV35S>RoC. The Ubi1, Act1, and Emu gave 12-, 8-, or 2-fold higher expression levels, respectively, compared with the CamV35S promoter.

Comparison of hpt and bar genes driven by various promoters for stable transformation. Embryogenic calli were cobombarded with pUbi1-*gus* and a range of plasmids containing either the *hph* or *bar* gene controlled by various promoters. Calli staining for GUS activity 1 d after shooting produced more than 300 blue expression units (BEUs) per petri dish of calli bombarded with each plasmid. Although most of the BEUs diminished or disappeared, a few from the pUbi1-*gus*-bombarded calli and any of the three *hph*-containing plasmids gradually increased in size over 2 wk of selection. Four weeks after selection, they formed nodular structures from the surface of the original calli.

Cobombardment of pUbi1-*gus* and pUbi1-*hph* gave the most large BEUs after 4 wk, pEmu-*hph* produced a similar number of smaller BEUs, and pCaMV35S-*hph* gave the fewest and smallest BEUs. Some cultures cobombarded with *gus* and *bar* constructs had modest increase in size and number of BEUs. None of the BEUs developed nodular structures.

Selection of stably transformed cell lines and regeneration of transgenic plants. Embryogenic calli were bombarded with

the *hph* gene constructs (pEmu-*hph* and pUbi1-*hph*) either alone or combined with the *gus* constructs (p40CSD35SAcl-*gus* and pUbi1-*gus*). With the cobombarded calli, about 300-1,500 BEUs were obtained 1 d after shooting.

Without staining for GUS activity, resulting transformed cells or microcalli cannot be identified under the dissecting microscope for at least 1 mo after bombardment. However, staining a few plates of target calli for GUS activity after 2 wk of selection allowed us to observe transformed cell clusters. After three to four subcultures on selection media, fast-growing callus lines could be distinguished among the bombarded calli. These callus lines were individually subcultured onto a new selection medium for further growth.

From 10 experiments and after 2 mo of selection on media, 50 transformed callus lines were obtained from 72 bombarded plates (see table). Of these, 16 regenerated into 79 putative transgenic plants (about 30% regeneration frequency) when placed onto the regeneration medium. Of the six putative transgenic plant lines from cotransformation of *gus* and *hph* genes, two were GUS-positive when the plants were about 5 cm tall. However, GUS activity of one line ceased as the plants matured. All 79 putative transgenic plants (24 sterile and 55 fertile) were transferred to soil in the glasshouse. Most of the sterile plants were derived from experiment 1, which used foundation callus line 1. About 87% of the transgenic plants derived from foundation callus lines 2 and 3 were fertile. Fertile plants were derived from 12 different transformed callus lines (6 from pUbi1-*hph* and 6 from pEmu-*hph*). Southern blot analysis showed that at least one plant from each line contained between one and eight copies of the transgene. Ten of the 12 transgenic plant lines contained both selectable and nonselectable genes, which were introduced on separate plasmids, giving an 83% cointegration frequency.

Calli bombarded with *bar* constructs grew poorly on bialaphos-containing media irrespective of the promoter used to control the *bar* gene. The few BEUs that expanded over time failed to form nodular cell clusters. This suggests the limited use of the *bar* gene in indica rice transformation. Rapid growth of hygromycin-resistant calli